

The Administration Model of Private Schools under KKPEO in 21st Century

Phrasophonphatthanapundit¹, Ekkarach Kositpimanvach², Phrakrupalad Boonchuay Auiwong³,
Chulapunpon Thanaphaet⁴, Phrahonda Khemma, Niraj Ruangsang⁵

¹Faculty of Education, ^{2,3,4,5} Faculty of Education, Mahachulalongkornrajavidyalaya University,
Khon Kaen Campus

ABSTRACT

This research aims at 1) studying the current and desirable conditions of the administration of private schools under the Khon Kaen Provincial Education Office (KKPEO) in the 21st century; 2) studying the administration model of private schools (AMPS) under KKPEO in the 21st century. The research operation was divided into 3 phases as follows: Phase 1: study the current condition and desirable locations to collect the quantitative data; the population used in the study included 128 administrators and 2,482 teachers (total 2,610) in 128 private schools under KKPEO. The samples in this study included 128 administrators and 232 teachers (total 360), selected by Simple Random Sampling. The five-rating scale questionnaire with its content validity of 0.86 and a coefficient of reliability of 0.92 was used as the research tool to collect the data. The necessary statistics such as Frequency, Percentage and Standard Deviation was used to analyze the obtained data. In Phase2: collect the qualitative data by organizing Focus Group Discussion with 10 experts, in this stage, a group discussion recording form was used to collect the data, later on analyzed by the content analysis in accordance with the conceptual framework and other issues. In Phase 3: collect the qualitative data from purposively selected stakeholders, 6 experts and 3 administrators, 15 teachers (a total of 24) from private schools with the excellent performance were invited for public hearings. The form of evaluation, verification and certification of research results was used as a research tool in this phase. The research results indicated that the administration of private schools under KKPEO in the 21st century was statistically rated in overall at a high level. The studied aspects were ranked according to their needs as follows: 1) technology implementation to promote management and learning; 2) curriculum development in line with social changes and life skills; 3) development of teaching and learning skills and innovation; 4) development of academic achievement and career; 5) building a network of learning.

Keywords

Thailand, private schools, administration, 21st century

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Introduction

In the 21st century (2001 – 2100), the world has changed rapidly and uncertainly as same as knowledge. Information system dramatically changes its trends to new directions. The worlds were all interconnected in a networked fashion. Humans have changed the way of living and work[1]. This turns the 21st century into an age of extremity. The world change in the 21st century has a great impact on the education sector as education administrators are highly expected from stakeholders under the more complication of educational management throughout the world[2].

In Thailand, Private School Act 2007 (Edition 2 in 2011) [3] defines the private educational institution or private school as an educational organization invested by private individuals under the Office of the Private Education Commission. Private educational institutions have always been a part of the Thai education system and have participated in the educational management of the country. It also

plays an important role in alleviating the burden of public sector responsibilities[3]. Therefore, with the role of private education institutions in Thailand, private schools cannot reject the educational change in the 21st century with the advancement of information technology and globalization, importantly leading people to make changes of lifestyle and operation in digital format due to the connection of information and unlimited access to learning resources. In the 21st century, it is necessary to adjust the learning management model in line with administrative challenges and changes such as a social state, way of life, access to technology, diversity and conflict and management efficiency[2] [4]. A tool for the management of private education institutions in this century is ‘the organizational learning management’, creating an organizational culture that facilitates transformation of networking and working with the learning establishments of the learners. The private schools must always be aware of change as a major concern. Currently, the competition between private and public

schools is very high in Thailand. Therefore, the private educational institutions need a suitable educational institution management model in order to effectively manage the schools despite effects of changes [5]. It is necessary to rely on management competency of the school administrators in developing educational institutions, improving the quality of education standards and the quality of learners to reach an international standard. One of the problems of private education institutions in Thailand is all the investment have been made by private individuals. Therefore, the development of the school must be done with caution in order to prevent financial loss and to gain stability, sustainability and popularity of parents and more students attendance every year. This leads to a need for constructing an administration model of private schools in the 21st century (AMPS) in order to stabilize the education institution with sustainable immunity, confidence and readiness to face change regardless of time, affiliation policy, law, politics, government, society, economy, objects, environment and globalization [6].

The 21st century has become the focus of many parties and the change has become more visible than in the past. Due to such change, it is essential to have a good management plan because fast educational movement creates more opportunities. Education management therefore is another important issue to keep pace with the changes, it is also a key mechanism to drive other sectors to be ready for such change [7]. In the 21st century, the private school administrators are responsible for the outcome of educational administration in their own schools in various areas such as academic achievement, desirable characteristics of students, career support, ICT proficiency and E-learning, developing the school as a learning community, building a network to promote learning and success, developing a curriculum updated to the social changes and life skills, using technology to promote learning management, and development of teaching and learning and innovation.

From the aforementioned problems and importance, as in the field of private education administration in Khon Kaen Province and lecturers in the Doctor of Education program Administration Mahachulalongkornrajavidyalaya University Khon Kaen Campus, the researchers are interested

in studying AMPS or 'the administration model of private educational institutions in the 21st century' under KKPEO. The benefits of this research will be used in the management of private schools in terms of policy formulation in the action planning to determine the direction for further private school development.

II. OBJECTIVES

The objectives of this research were: 1) to study the current and desirable conditions of the administration of private schools under KKPEO in the 21st century; 2) to study AMPS under KKPEO in the 21st century.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The methodology of this mixed methods research is as follows:

1) Population, samples and target group

1. The population of this research included 128 administrators and 2,482 teachers (in total 2,610).

2. The samples of this study were 128 school administrators, selected by Purposive Sampling and 2) 232 teachers, selected by Simple Random Sampling.

3. The target group included 3.1) 10 experts invited to participate in Focus Group Discussion (FGD) [8] and selected by Purposive Sampling; namely, experts, Khon Kaen provincial education officers, directors of Private Education Promotion Group, private school principals with Ph.D. in Education Administration. 3.2) Stakeholders, selected by Purposive Sampling and invited to participate in the public hearings, included 6 experts in schools with excellent performance in Khon Kaen Province, school administrators, 1 from each school and teachers, 5 from each (in total 24).

2. Research Instruments

The research instruments were used in 3 phases as follows:

Phase 1: collect the quantitative data by using questionnaires, divided into 3 parts: Part 1: the check list questionnaire on the general status of the informant; Part 2: the 5-rating scale questionnaire on current and desirable conditions of private schools in the 21st century under KKPEO; Part 3: the open-ended questions to

obtain recommendations on the administration of private schools in the 21st century under KKPEO.

Phase 2: collect the qualitative data by conducting FGD of 10 experts as informants, selected by Purposive Sampling. A tool used in FGD was a recording form.

Phase 3: collect qualitative data by using public hearing, informants in this phase were 6 stakeholders or qualified persons in Khon Kaen private schools with excellent performance, consisting of 6 experts and 3 administrators, 15 teachers (a total of 24). The instrument used was the form of assessment, verification and confirmation of AMPS under KKPEO.

3. Data Analysis

The study in Phase 1 used a data analysis software package to analyze the following statistical values: 1) the data on the status of the respondents were statistically analyzed by using frequency and percentage values; 2) current and desirable levels, the administration of private schools in the 21st century under KKPEO statistically analyzed by using mean and standard deviation, necessary needs (PNI_{modified}); 3) content analysis was used to study the recommendations before being integrated in the private school administration model in the 21st century.

The study in Phase 2 analyzed the data obtained from FGD including content analysis according to the conceptual framework and other issues encountered before making a summary.

The study in Phase 3 analyzed 50% or more of the frequency (f) of the assessment form

to validate and approve the private school administration model in the 21st century in terms of appropriateness, usefulness and possibilities.

IV. RESEARCH RESULTS

From Table 1 below, it was found that the current state of the administration of private educational institutions in the 21st century under KKPEO. The overall mean was at a moderate level ($\bar{x} = 3.50$, S.D = .34). When considering each aspect, it was found that the aspect which the samples had the highest level of opinion was the building of the learning network ($\bar{x} = 4.16$, S.D = .75), followed by the development of academic achievement and career ($\bar{x} = 3.59$, SD = .71) and the aspect with the lowest mean was technology implementation to promote management and learning ($\bar{x} = 2.96$, S.D = .85) respectively.

For the desirable status of the administration of private schools in the 21st century under KKPEO, the overall mean was at the highest level ($\bar{x} = 4.56$, S.D = .29). Based on the studied aspect consideration, it was found that the subject with the highest level of opinion of the samples was 'focusing on improving academic achievement and career' ($\bar{x} = 4.70$, S.D = .47), followed by the field of learning network building ($\bar{x} 4.68$, S.D = .46) And the item with the lowest mean was the technology implementation to promote management and learning ($\bar{x} = 4.39$, S.D = .49), respectively.

Private school administration model in the 21 st century	Current Status			Desirable Status			PNI Modified	Order of PNI Modified
	\bar{x}	S.D.	Level	\bar{x}	S.D.	Level		
1. Curriculum development in line with social change and life skills	3.29	.50	moderate	4.41	.49	high	0.34	2
2. Development of teaching and learning skills and innovation	3.53	.75	high	4.65	.50	highest	0.32	3
3. Implementing technology to promote management and	2.96	.85	moderate	4.39	.49	high	0.49	1

learning								
4. Focusing on improving academic achievement and career	3.59	.71	high	4.70	.47	highest	0.31	4
5. Building a learning network	4.16	.75	high	4.68	.46	highest	0.12	5
Overall	3.50	.34	moderate	4.56	.29	highest	0.30	

Table 1: AMPS in the 21st century under KKPEO

When sorting of importance of essential needs by identifying the needs that are more important than the mean of the PNI_{modified} index of .30, it was found that Item 3 'the technology promotes management and learning' needs to be developed first ($PNI_{\text{modified}} = 0.49$); followed by Item 1 'curriculum development in line with social change and life skills' ($PNI_{\text{modified}} = 0.34$) and the least, Item 4 'focusing on improving academic achievement and career'. The researcher has brought the results as mentioned to manage the private schools in the 21st century under KKPEO in order of importance of essential needs as follows: 1) implementation of technology to promote management and learning; 2) development of curriculum in accordance with the changes of society and life skills; 3) development of teaching and learning skills and innovation; 4) focusing on improving academic achievement and career. For building a learning network with the value ($PNI_{\text{modified}} = 0.12$), its score was less than the PNI_{modified} average value. At first, it was eliminated. However, in FGD, the experts have resolved to maintain it as it is considered an integral part of AMSP in the 21st century.

AMSP in the 21st century under KKPEO are as follows: 1) Implementing technology to promote management and learning: 1) use computers to increase management efficiency in various aspects such as administration, finance and accounting; 2) organize administrative information system using ICT; 3) use of information technology in communication and coordination; 4) encourage teachers and students to use ICT to develop teaching and learning; 5) encourage teachers and students to search and learn information from the Internet.

2) Curriculum development in accordance with changes in society and life skills: 1) develop a learning curriculum according to one's ability; 2)

provide opportunities and freedom to choose learning according to the students' interests; 3) support teachers and students to manage learning with a focus on solving life and social problems; 4) encourage teachers to develop students according to changing conditions to create integration of learners' life and society; 5) develop curriculum in accordance with the 21st century skills.

3) Development of teaching and learning skills and innovation: 1) to respond the needs of learners and parents; 2) learners have been completely developed in all aspects with quality; 3) develop outstanding academic quality and create empirical work; 4) build teaching and learning skills to be visible to society to create confidence and acceptance; 5) encourage teachers and students to create new innovations.

4) Focusing on developing academic achievement and career: 1) manage schools aiming to improve the learning achievement of learners; 2) develop teachers to increase their potential of academic work; 3) encourage teachers to use teaching results to further improve and develop; 4) administrators should organize regular internal supervision of teaching and learning; 5) encourage teachers to use a variety of measurement tools; 6) promote learning activities that focus on work and career.

5) Building a learning network: 1) connect groups of people with objectives and interest in academics to create a network; 2) constantly conduct the network learning activities according the objectives of the groups; 3) arrange academic networking activities that school administrators can create the relationship with experts; 4) create sustainable academic networking activities.

V. DISCUSSION

According to the research, the current status of administration of private schools in the 21st century under KKPEO in overall was statically

rated at a moderate level. This means that the administrators of private schools under KKPEO had a moderate level of opinion on the administration of private schools in the 21st century. This is consistent with the study of Pataranit Puttiruengsak in 2017[9], showing that 21st century school administrators still need to develop knowledge and experience to support the changes in the world society in the globalization era, to prepare for the 21st century. The overall desirable status was statistically rated at the highest level. This means that the administrators of private schools know how to manage schools in the 21st century, realize the direction in the administration of schools to advance in the future. This is consistent with the work of Pipud Gapajoon (2014) [10], which studied the characteristics of 21st century school administrators according to teachers' views of Thabodin Network Group under the Office of the Sakaeo Primary Educational Service Area 2, which showed that the school administrators must develop themselves and adjust the management guidelines in line with the changes of the world society in the 21st century with operation to create the learning achievement outcomes, to develop a curriculum that integrates social skills and life skills, to apply the curriculum to build integration, to use technology to promote curriculum and learning networking.

The first priority of needs that should be developed is to implement technology to promote management and learning. This is in line with the work of Wisava Polkong, (2019) [7] suggesting that administrators should develop teachers and staff to have knowledge and skills in creating online media, use of digital platforms in the management of learning and develop learning materials according to the nature of each course; administrators should take the lead in using technology to promote the implementation of the curriculum to bring knowledge and experience to develop learners. The second priority needs to be developed is to develop a curriculum in accordance with social changes and life skills, consistent with Montatip Numnu (2018) [11] which studied the skills of 21st century school administrators under the Office of Pathumthani Primary Educational Service Area 2, indicating that the administrators should develop a curriculum, aligned with the 21st century social conditions, emphasizing integration of social

skills, life skills, in the context of change by arranging a stakeholder meeting to determine the targeted needs in terms of social skills, life skills in line with the learning skills in the 21st century. The third priority needs to be developed are: development of teaching and learning skills and innovation, the administrators should be an integrated learning management development policy for all subjects aligned with 21st century learning skills encouraging teachers and students to create innovations. The fourth need priority is aimed at developing academic and professional achievement, administrators should develop work practices aimed at learning achievement with learners, a network of parents, local communities and stakeholders to propose ways to allow opportunities for all sectors to participate in developing academic achievement by giving opportunities for those involved to participate in learning and exchange activities. For the focus on student achievement, administrators must have knowledge and understanding of objectives of education management for creating the skills of the learners in the 21st century to be used in school administration for efficiency and effectiveness. Administrators should focus on developing learners into careers in line with the 21st century. For a fifth need priority, for the work of building a learning network, although the quantitative research results were $PNI_{\text{modified}} = 0.12$, which was lower than the mean $PNI_{\text{modified}} = .30$, which indicates that it was not the important need, the groups of experts participated in FGD and stakeholders joined in the public hearings agreed that it should be there even though it is the fifth priority. In other words, it should also be part of AMPS in the 21st century, in line with the concept of Snowden (2005) [12] mentioning that the learning network is the structured space of learning, where people with the same interests come together and have a social bond that binds members together. It is the center to promote communication, create interactions in organizing activities of people in school. This is consistent with the guidelines of Sasitra Plerjit (2014) [13] that studied the 21st century administrative skills of basic education institution administrators under the Office of Nakhon Pathom Primary Educational Service Area 1, mentioned that the school administrators should use academic leadership in the 21st century to connect groups of people with learning interests, regularly

participating in network activities with community and organizations, private organizations, professional organizations, establishment, educational association, organize activities for all parties to participate in network construction with exchange of knowledge, create leaders and followers in the building of academic networks, arrange a study visit, develop knowledge for excellence and organize activities both inside and outside the school.

VI. SUGGESTIONS

1) Suggestions for the use of research results

1.1 Implementation of technology to promote management and learning: administrators should use computers to increase efficiency in administrative management, finance, accounting and database management; create an administrative information system, coordination, communication; encourage personnel and students to use ICT to develop teaching and learning and search and learn from the Internet.

1.2 Curriculum development in line with changes in society and life skills: administrators must develop courses for learners according to one's own ability, allow them to freedom to choose the content of study according to their interests; Focus on solving life and social problems: they should promote the development of learners according to changing conditions for the integration of students' life and society and 21st century skills.

1.3 Development of teaching and learning skills and innovation: administrators must develop teaching and learning skills according to the needs of learners and parents in order to develop in all areas with quality, develop academic work to be outstanding, create an empirical contribution to society, build confidence to get acceptance and promote the creation of new innovations.

1.4 Developing academic achievement and career: administrators must strive to develop higher academic achievement, to increase academic potential, to encourage teachers to bring about academic achievement to improve and develop their work and plan to use it better, to arrange teaching supervision with various measuring and evaluation tools that focus on organizing work and career activities.

1.5 Building a learning network, administrators should establish Memorandum of Understanding (MOU) with the educational

institutions within and outside of the country to build academic networks and have a common PLC process.

2) Suggestions for the next research

2.1 Participatory action research should be conducted. This research may be used as a guideline, such as the development of the indicators found.

2.2 There should be research on creating and compiling the assessment form of indicators of administration of private schools in the 21st century as a tool for evaluating the administration of private schools.

2.3 Research should be conducted on the development of indicators of administration of schools under other affiliations to obtain school administration indicators suitable for that context.

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